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Independent Research

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Weather, Water, and the Bite: A Field Study on Bullseye Snakehead Feeding Behavior in South
Florida

The bullseye snakehead (*Channa marulius*) is one of the most aggressive predators taking over South Florida's freshwater canals, and I've seen up close how fast it's spreading. Originally from Southeast Asia, it can breathe air, survive in highly polluted water, and strike its prey with explosive speeds. Since it appeared in Broward County in the early 2000s, bullseye snakeheads have spread widely across neighborhood canals. They hunt native species such as Peacock Bass, Largemouth Bass and Bluegill, and are actively throwing off the balance of the canal system.

Through my conservation initiative, Florida Fish Mission, I've focused on targeting these invasives while collecting data on their behavior. Florida Fish Mission began as a small community project to clean canals and remove invasive species, but quickly it grew into something bigger. I started logging catches, noting weather changes, and watching how the fish acted each day under different conditions. Over time, I realized there might be a real pattern happening around me. Some days the water was overwhelmed with blowups and surface strikes, while others were completely still with no activity. This study was conducted to help develop a clearer understanding of this species' feeding behavior and to aid future removal efforts by Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC), ultimately helping to limit the population of this increasing problem in my community and across South Florida.

Methods

Between January and August 2025, I recorded multiple sessions targeting this species in lakes, canals, and ponds throughout my community in Sunrise, Florida. Each session was aimed specifically at bullseye snakeheads. During each outing, I logged the number of fish caught and noted the overall activity of the waterway. My main setups were topwater frog lures (sometimes paired with a flashlight for spotting), fluke lures, and Super Spook Jr. lures. Sessions shorter than thirty minutes were not included in my study because they were not long enough to show consistent activity.

For each date, I collected historical weather data from sources such as WeatherSpark, focusing on conditions such as temperature, rainfall, cloud cover, wind, and barometric pressure. Temperatures ranged from 75 to 98 °F, and rainfall ranged from 0 to 1.2 inches. I categorized each day as high-pressure, falling-pressure, or steady pressure, basing each on weather charts. My field notes included whether I saw “blowups” (water splashes on the surface), cruising snakeheads, or signs of baitfish near the surface. Typically, the days with low activity had little to none of these conditions and the snakeheads seen would act skittishly and would be scared by slight movements or sounds

Results

Condition Combination	Average Catch Rate (Fish/hr)	Surface Activity	Example Dates
Warm, (80-85 °F), cloudy, falling pressure, with light rain	2.3	Frequent blowups, multiple strikes	May 14th, May 16th
Warm (80-90 °F), cloudy, steady pressure, dry	1.1	Occasional strikes	April 29th
Hot (Over 90 °F), clear, high, pressure	0.2	Fish are visible but inactive	June 8th

Warm (80-85 °F), clear skies, with rising pressure	0.3	Little to no surface activity	May 30th
Moderate (75-80 °F), cloudy, with falling pressure	1.7	Short bursts of activity near dusk	April 12th

Observations and Field Notes

Over dozens of sessions, three environmental factors consistently influenced snakehead behavior: light and cloud cover, rain and storm activity, and barometric pressure.

Light and Cloud Cover: Cloudy days or late afternoons typically had far more surface movement than bright, sunny ones. On clear days, snakeheads often stayed tucked deep under lily pads or beneath floating vegetation where lures couldn't reach. During cloudy evenings, they moved closer towards the banks and hit topwater frogs aggressively. This supports the idea that low light helps ambush predators hunt more effectively by reducing how easily prey can detect threats. Santon et al. observed that, "light redirection by small, diurnal fish significantly contributes to their ability to visually detect cryptic predators," (Santon et al.). This means that conditions with more light give prey the advantage of helping them spot predators sooner. When light is decreased, prey becomes less aware, and predators such as the bullseye snakeheads tend to feed more successfully.

Rain and Storm Activity: When there was light rain, it almost always triggered activity. On several occasions, like May 14, as soon as the first drops hit the surface, I saw immediate blowups within minutes. Baitfish began to scatter and snakeheads came out from the banks to feed. After heavy summer storms, however, the opposite happened and the activity went dead. I predict that runoff and excessive disturbance pushed conditions past a useful window. This pattern fits known rain effects in the short-term, in how rainfall increases surface oxygenation

and alters sub-surface conditions in which fish respond to (“Dissolved Oxygen | US EPA”). It also aligns with work showing that rain events can rapidly fish the activity rhythms of fish (Payne et al.). Over the course of my study, too much runoff seemed to restrict bullseye snakeheads’ feeding behavior entirely. On the other hand, light rain produced the most consistent feeding windows for snakeheads.

Barometric Pressure: Pressure changes had the clearest effect of all conditions tested. On falling-pressure days, snakeheads fed heavily, especially before or during storms. On high-pressure days, they were inactively ignoring lures altogether. I often saw them swimming near the surface, motionless, even when everything else looked perfect. My biggest catch, a 9.5-pounder on May 16, came during a steady pressure drop that started earlier that afternoon. When combinations of the factors studied lined up, such as cloud cover with mild rain and dropping pressure, the behavior of snakeheads increased dramatically. In less than an hour, I could catch several fish in the same area of water. Although, if only one or a couple factors lined up, like clouds without rain, results were mixed.

Discussion

This study reinforces what many local anglers know but rarely document: bullseye snakeheads respond strongly to weather. They feed most aggressively under low light and pre-storm pressure drops. Their activity overall seems to depend on a mix of sensory and environmental triggers.

During fieldwork, I also took note of a few patterns that weren’t formally measured but could matter. In heavily vegetated areas, snakeheads rose closer to the surface late in the day. This could be tied to oxygen released by aquatic plants through photosynthesis. Lure presentation also made a difference. During the day, more natural-colored frogs like green or tan

worked best, while at night darker or high-contrast lures (black or white frogs) produced better results. It's possible that in low light, snakeheads hunt their prey based more on vibration and silhouette than color.

There were also strange outlier days. I'd see fish sitting at the surface, following the frog slowly, then drifting away. Sometimes they spooked instantly when a flashlight beam hit the water. Overall, my observations show that the snakehead bite follows consistent environmental cues. A combination of cloud cover, mild rain, and falling pressure brings them out. Yet, too much light, heavy storming/rain, or high pressure shuts down their appetite.

Conclusion

Based on months of field data, the bullseye snakehead's feeding behavior is most affected by three key factors: low light, recent rainfall, and falling barometric pressure. When these conditions overlap, activity spikes. No single condition guarantees a strike, but these conditions in harmonious combinations create clear "windows" of activity.

Understanding these patterns is important for management and removal efforts. Targeting snakeheads during these feeding windows can make clean-ups and angler-based removals far more effective. In my own work with Florida Fish Mission, this information helps my team plan better canal outings and community events focused on protecting native fish species.

Future research could measure additional variables such as moon phase, dissolved oxygen, or water clarity to build a fuller picture of what drives snakehead behavior. Even though this study is on a smaller scale, projects like this can contribute to better strategies of managing invasive species in South Florida and may ultimately help stabilize snakehead populations within the ecosystem.

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